

Bleeding Gums: Cause and Treatment

Lily James*

Editorial Office, Journal of Dental Research and Practice, Belgium

Corresponding Author*

Editorial Office,
Journal of Dental Research and Practice,
Belgium
E-mail: dentistry@emedscholar.com

Copyright: 2022 James L. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Received: 03-Mar-2022, Manuscript No. jdrp-22-60531; **Editor assigned:** 05-Mar-2022, PreQC No. jdrp-22-60531 (PQ); **Reviewed:** 15-Mar-2022, QC No. jdrp-22-60531 (Q); **Revised:** 15-Mar-2022, Manuscript No. jdrp-22-60531 (R); **Published:** 20-Mar-2022, DOI: 10.4172/jdrp.22.4(1).005

Commentary

Bleeding gums can be an indication that you have or may foster gum illness. Continuous gum Bleeding might be because of plaque development on the teeth. It can likewise be an indication of a serious medical Condition [1].

Mostly the cause of bleeding gums can be brought about by cleaning your teeth too energetically or wearing false teeth that don't fit accurately. The Main Reason of Bleeding gum is the development of plaque at the gum line. This will prompt a condition called gingivitis, or inflamed gums [2].

Plaque that isn't taken out will solidify into tartar. This will prompt expanded bleeding and a further developed type of gum and jaw bone illness known as periodontitis.

Causes

- Bleeding Gums can be caused by Many Reasons Like,
- Any bleeding disorders
- Brushing too hard
- Hormonal changes during pregnancy
- Ill-fitting dentures or other dental appliances
- Improper flossing
- Infection, which can be either in a tooth or the gum
- Leukemia, a type of blood cancer
- Scurvy, a vitamin C deficiency
- Use of blood thinners
- Vitamin K deficiency [3]

Few other causes of Gums bleeding are:

- Individuals who wear dentures (false teeth) likewise may in some cases experience bleeding gums. This is almost certain when dentures fit too firmly.

- Converse with your dental specialist or orthodontist on the off chance that false teeth or other oral apparatuses are making your gums bleed. They might have to take new impressions to make a superior fitting mouthpiece.
- Pregnancy is ordinarily a reason for gum Bleeding. Hormonal changes that happen during pregnancy can make the gums more touchy.
- Bleeding issues like hemophilia and leukemia can likewise expand your gamble of bleeding gums. Your gums could drain on a more regular basis assuming you take blood-diminishing meds. Drugs in this class incorporate warfarin, ibuprofen, and heparin [4].

Treatment of Bleeding Gums

- Great dental cleanliness is the initial step to overseeing draining gums.
- Visit your dental specialist two times every year for proficient cleaning. Your dental specialist will inform you as to whether you have gum disease and show you how to appropriately clean your teeth. Legitimate brushing and flossing can eliminate plaque from your gum line and decrease your gamble of creating periodontal sickness.
- Your dental specialist may likewise tell you the best way to utilize a sterile mouthwash to limit plaque that structures in your mouth. Also, a wash of warm salt water can assist with alleviating enlarged gums that drain without any problem.
- Utilize a delicate toothbrush. It'll be delicate on excited gums, particularly in the event that you experience draining in the wake of cleaning your teeth. Medium and hard fibers might be excessively rough for your sensitive gums.
- You could likewise think about utilizing a rotating brush. The uncommonly planned brush heads on these toothbrushes can assist you with cleaning your gum line more effectively than a manual toothbrush.
- Practice great oral medical services, including brushing double a day and flossing one time each day.
- Substitution of toothbrushes each 3 to 4 months.
- Visit the dental specialist routinely.
- Abstain from smoking or work with a specialist to stop smoking.
- Eat a solid eating routine that incorporates bunches of new products of the soil and breaking point handled food sources and food sources with added sugars [5].

References

1. Robinson, K.M. "Bleeding gums and your health." WebMD
2. Roth, E. "What you need to know about bleeding gums" Healthline (2019).
3. Kapner, M. "Bleeding gums" MedlinePlus (2020).
4. Caryn. "10 causes of bleeding gums." Delta Dental (2021).
5. Medcover Hospitals. "Bleeding gums." (2021).